

CHRISTOPHER MARLOWE
IS “THE FATHER OF ENGLISH TRAGEDY”

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Annotation: Christopher Marlowe was a great English dramatist, poet and translator of the Elizabethan era. Furthermore, he is considered to be the first English playwright to reveal the full potential of dramatic blank verse and the first to exploit the tragic implications of Renaissance humanism.

Marlowe was the foremost Elizabethan tragedian of his day who belonged to the group of university-educated practitioners of literature known collectively as the ‘University Wits’. [2, p. 111] He greatly influenced William Shakespeare, who was born in the same year as Marlowe and who rose to become the preeminent Elizabethan playwright after Marlowe’s mysterious early death.

Marlowe’s tragedy is significant due to its newness, renaissance influence, Machiavellian morality, powerful and passionate expressions, element of tragic inner conflict, overreaching protagonists, popular literary style, high seriousness, bombastic language and blank verse. Swinburne remarks: ‘Before him, there was neither genuine blank verse nor genuine tragedy in our language. After his arrival the way was prepared and the paths were made straight for Shakespeare.’

Marlowe’s contribution to English tragedy is very vital and manifold. He has rightly been called the ‘Morning Star’ of the great Elizabethan drama. It was in the fifteenth century that tragedy came into English dramatic field. And this was due to the influence of the Revival of Learning and the translation of great Italian tragedies of Seneca. Although this tragedy showed some innovation, yet most of the Senecan characteristics, long-sententious speeches, lack of action, talkative ghosts and horrible scenes of murder were very much there. The credit goes to Marlowe to liberate the Elizabethan drama from the worst features of the Senecan tragedy. One

can discuss various characteristics of his tragedy to point out how he formulated the English drama, specially the tragedy which was improved upon and perfected by a genius like Shakespeare.

Marlowe put forward a new kind of a tragic hero. The medieval concept of tragedy was the fall of a great man, kings or royal personalities. But it was left to Marlowe to create the real tragic hero. Almost all the heroes of Marlowe such as Tamburlaine, Faustus or Jew of Malta are of humble parentage, but they are endowed with great heroic qualities and they are really great men. His tragedy is, in fact, the tragedy of the hero. All other characters of Marlowian drama look insignificant besides the towering personality of the tragic hero.

Marlowe revived the Aristotelian conception of a tragic hero in so far as he introduced a certain flaw or flaws in his character. His heroes are men fired with indomitable passion and inordinate ambition. His Tamburlaine is in full-flooded pursuit of military and political power, his Faustus sells his soul to the devil to attain ultimate power through knowledge and his Jew of Malta discards all human values in order to gain maximum wealth. But they are perished by the forces beyond their control. Another great achievement of Marlowe was to introduce the element of conflict, especially inner struggle in two of his great tragedies like Doctor Faustus and Edward. And this inner conflict reveals the real significance of character as the main stay of a great tragedy. It should be highlighted that one of the notable characteristics of Marlowe's tragedies is its high seriousness and hence, there is complete lack of humor.

According to many critics, the scenes of clownishness in Doctor Faustus are nothing but later interpolations. He often neglects female characters. Marlowe's poetic excellence was highly appreciated even by his contemporaries. Swinburne plays his tribute:

“The first great English poet was the father of English tragedy and the creator of English blank verse.”[4, p. 153].

All of Marlowe's heroes, Faustus is the most poetic, as he is a prototype of

Marlowe himself with his passionate love of beauty and yearning for sensuous pleasure.

Was this the face that launched a thousand ships,

And burnt the topless towers of Ilium?

Sweet Helen makes me immortal with a kiss.

A new spirit of poetry was breathed into the artificial and monotonous verse of old plays. He made a blank verse a great dramatic medium acknowledged by all his successors as the metre indispensable for any serious drama.

As far as a plot construction is concerned all of Marlowe's great plays, with the exception of *Edward* to some extent, suffer from great technical defects. There are no subplots in his dramas. Whatever the particular focus of modern critics, biographers and novelists, for his contemporaries in the literary world, Marlowe was above all an admired and influential artist. Within weeks of his death, George Peele remembered him as "Marley, the Muses' darling", Michael Drayton noted that "He had in him those brave translunary things that the first poets had", and Ben Jonson wrote of "Marlowe's mighty line". Thomas Nashe wrote warmly of his friend, "poor deceased Kit Marlowe".

Among the few contemporary dramatists to say anything negative about Marlowe was the anonymous author of the Cambridge University play 'The return from Parnassus' who wrote:

'Pity it is that wit so ill should dwell,

Wit lent from heaven,

But vices sent from hell.'

The most famous tribute to Marlowe was paid by William Shakespeare. He was heavily influenced by Marlowe in his work, as can be seen in the reusing of Marlowian themes in *Antony and Cleopatra*, *The Merchant of Venice*, *Richard III* and *Macbeth*. In *Hamlet*, after meeting with the travelling actors, Hamlet requests the player to perform a speech about the Trojan War, at which has an echo of Marlowe's *Dido, Queen Carthage*. In 'Love's Labour's Lost', Shakespeare

brings on a character 'Marcade' in conscious acknowledgement of Marlowe's character 'Mercury', in 'The Massacre at Paris'. [5, p.4]

"Marlowe gave the drama passion and poetry. Drama was his most precious gift. Shakespeare would not have been Shakespeare, if Marlowe had never written or lived. He might not have been altogether Shakespeare people know." [6, p.16]

Although a number of English dramatist before Christopher Marlowe had achieved some notable success in the field of comedy, none had produced a first-rate tragedy. It was Marlowe who made the first significant advances in tragedy. In each of his major plays, he focuses on a single character who dominates the action by virtue of his extraordinary strength of will. Marlowe's thundering blank verse, although for the most part lacking the subtlety of Shakespeare's mature poetry, proved a remarkably effective medium for this kind of drama.

References:

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5. Robert A. Logan, Shakespeare's Marlowe (2007) pp. 4.
6. Constance Kuriyama, Christopher Marlowe: A Renaissance Life (2002). pp 16.